

Utility in context: A sociohistorical lens for examining students' conceptions of the usefulness of mathematics

Tracy E. Dobie, University of Utah, tracy.dobie@utah.edu

Rachel Carlsruh, University of Utah

Daniel K. Aina Jr., University of Utah

As the emphasis on mathematics in our society has increased, so too have discussions of the usefulness of mathematics. Research has highlighted many benefits of viewing mathematics as useful, from increased performance to enhanced interest. However, we argue that discussions of usefulness have largely been devoid of context, and that to understand current ideas about the usefulness of mathematics, we must consider them in relation to narratives of economic competition and global dominance. Here we propose applying a sociohistorical lens to students' discussions of the usefulness of mathematics, exploring the case of one student to consider what such a lens can offer. We conclude by raising questions about the risks of perpetuating and potential benefits of rethinking existing narratives about the usefulness of mathematics.

Introduction

Discussions of mathematics education in the United States are often filled with questions and claims about applications, or usefulness, of mathematics. Students are encouraged to pursue advanced courses and learning opportunities in order to secure careers that require mathematics, such as those in engineering and information technology. And for students who are not interested in math-related careers, we often try to convince students of the usefulness of mathematics by explaining how math can be used to split checks with friends at a restaurant, balance budgets, or calculate discounts when shopping.

In recent decades, there has been an increasing push to consider the sociopolitical context of mathematics education (e.g., Gutiérrez, 2013; Valero, 2004), as well how various aspects of the historical context have shaped our understanding and assumptions of processes related to learning and learners (e.g., Philip & Sengupta, 2020; Schoenfeld, 2004). When applying these lenses to consider discussions around the usefulness of mathematics, numerous questions arise: Why and how have specific narratives about the usefulness of mathematics developed? Who benefits from the framing of mathematics as useful in these ways? Whose voices and histories are not represented in current rhetoric regarding the usefulness of mathematics?

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In this work, we place the notion of usefulness in context, exploring some of the ways in which the history of racial capitalism and emphasis on global dominance in the United States have influenced ideas about usefulness. In particular, we explore the following question: What new understandings can be made visible by applying a sociohistorical lens to the construct of usefulness? We address this question by first highlighting the sociohistorical context of mathematics education, with particular attention to the United States. Then we overview research on utility value as related to mathematics education and propose the value of applying a sociohistorical lens to understand narratives about the usefulness of mathematics. We propose that this lens can be productive for understanding students' talk about usefulness, illustrating this approach with the case of 13-year-old Liliana. We conclude by considering what that approach allowed us to see—as well as what silences it made visible—and raising questions for collective consideration moving forward.

Sociohistorical influences on mathematics education

In order to consider current ideas around the usefulness of mathematics in context, we begin by briefly exploring the sociohistorical context of mathematics education, with particular attention to our local context, the United States. Around the globe, scholars have highlighted how mathematics as a field has been positioned in service of capitalism and global competition (e.g., Greer & Mukhopadhyay, 2003; Valero, 2017). In the United States, Gutstein (2009) describes how mathematics education “is framed as a way to serve capital and to continue U.S. global dominance” (p. 138). He explores a range of influential reports that emphasize the importance of strengthening our global competitiveness through an emphasis on STEM and the need to prepare our workforce to meet the needs of STEM-centric jobs. Gutstein unpacks how the American Competitiveness Initiative (Domestic Policy Council, 2006) was developed as a mechanism to achieve these aims, and how the primary beneficiary is not the majority of the U.S. but rather the wealthy and corporations.

Furthermore, many STEM initiatives have been touted for promoting equity and making STEM accessible for all; however, researchers have repeatedly shown how such initiatives continue to perpetuate inequities and actually serve capitalism and U.S. economic interests (e.g., Bullock, 2017; Morales-Doyle & Gutstein, 2019). For example, Morales-Doyle and Gutstein (2019) highlight how STEM schools in Chicago claim to promote equity but actually serve the interests of racial capitalism (Robinson, 2000) by seeking to attract white, middle class families; prioritizing the interests of corporations; and perpetuating racist tracking practices. Vossoughi and Vakil (2018) highlight the connections between STEM education and militarism in the U.S., making visible how narratives about the need for diversity and equity in STEM education are often rooted in concerns for national security and global competitiveness. These various examples highlight how increasing calls in the U.S. for more diversity and equity in STEM are often in the interest of the nation and not indicative of a true commitment to people (e.g., Martin, 2009).

Alongside this sociohistorical positioning of mathematics education, exclusionary norms have developed regarding what it means to do mathematics in the U.S. In particular,

mathematics and mathematics education have been constructed as white, patriarchal spaces (e.g., Batten & Leyva, 2016; Stinson, 2013) with associated white male values, such as speed, competition, and independence (e.g., Leyva, 2021). These norms have resulted in the exclusion of Black, Latinx, and Indigenous students (e.g., Leyva et al., 2021) and influenced who has had access to mathematics and been viewed as belonging in STEM spaces. Before applying this sociohistorical lens to the construct of usefulness, we provide a brief overview of research on utility value in mathematics.

Perceived utility in mathematics

Currently, the concept of perceived usefulness—often referred to in terms of “utility value”—in mathematics has been examined from the field of educational psychology and has largely been investigated without much consideration of context. Research has described utility value as the degree to which a task is “useful and relevant for other aspects of [one’s] life” (Harackiewicz et al., 2012, p. 1), and studies have focused largely on interventions to enhance utility value and to explore the effects of perceiving a subject or task as useful. Two primary types of interventions have been explored. One focuses on direct communication of utility value, where educators or researchers explain the usefulness of certain subjects or tasks to students and then explore what impact that has (e.g., Durik et al., 2014). In such studies, applications of mathematics tend to focus on usefulness for everyday life in general, specific daily activities (especially those focused on money), careers, and current or future schooling (Dobie, 2019). A second type of intervention focuses on self-generated ideas about utility, where participants come up with their own applications of various techniques or tasks (e.g., Hulleman et al., 2010). Some recent work in this area has begun to characterize the connections students make and has identified a focus on community and connection to others—previously absent from this work—among first-generation under-represented minority college students (Harackiewicz et al., 2016). Across these various studies, researchers have found that perceived usefulness can have numerous positive benefits including enhanced interest in a subject and improved course performance (Hulleman et al., 2010; Hulleman & Harackiewicz, 2009). However, some limitations of these studies include the fact that they typically involve white, middle-class college students, and they are often not responsive to students’ sociocultural contexts or the larger history of mathematics education in the United States (Dobie, 2019).

In one study seeking to expand whose voices were represented in discussions of the usefulness, Dobie (2019) examined perspectives on the usefulness of mathematics among 84 seventh-grade students (mean age = 12.7 years), the majority of whom identified as Mexican, Mexican-American, or Chicana (76%). Students’ conceptions of usefulness (related to how mathematics content could be applied in their lives) were coded as focused on job/career, everyday life (general), daily activities, or current or future schooling. Across a range of survey and interview responses, nearly 70% of responses mentioned specific daily activities math could be useful for, and more than 50% of responses cited usefulness for everyday life in general and usefulness for one’s job or career. Zooming in on the daily activities category

revealed an emphasis on money-related activities, with 45.8% of those responses focusing on managing money (e.g., paying bills, budgeting, paying taxes) and 41.7% of those responses focusing on using math when buying and selling. Within the job/career category, students primarily focused on applications of mathematics to future jobs in general (63% of responses), though 33% of the responses mentioned application to a specific job, such as being a cashier, teacher, business owner, architect, or banker. Relatively few responses focused on the usefulness of mathematics for getting a job (4%), rather than performing a job.

Applying a sociohistorical lens to perceived utility in mathematics

Building on these findings from Dobie (2019), the current research considers the affordances of applying a sociohistorical perspective to explore adolescents' perceptions of the usefulness of mathematics. In particular, we argue for an examination of young people's talk about the usefulness of mathematics through the lens of long-standing narratives emphasizing STEM in service of capital, global dominance, and economic competitiveness. We apply this lens to the discourse of middle school students in a large urban area in the midwestern United States who were surveyed and interviewed about their perceptions of, experiences with, and ideas about the usefulness of mathematics. Here we offer one example of what such a lens might elucidate by examining the case of Liliana. We selected Liliana's case to explore here because of the prevalence of many common student narratives in her survey and interview responses. By applying this lens, we can consider how the sociohistorical context of national narratives about mathematics can influence adolescents' ways of thinking about the usefulness of mathematics.

The case of Liliana

Liliana was a 13-year-old female who identified herself as Mexican/Chicana. In her survey, she reported that mathematics was the most useful subject to learn because, "Whether buying coffee or a car, basic principles of math are in play." When asked during her interview to explain what she meant by "basic principles of math," she said the following:

Um, so Miss Martinez always tells us that you're gonna need math in everything you're doing. She was telling about us today [sic] as well because students are complaining, like, how does this help us in life? Um, when are we gonna need this? Well, like well you're gonna need, you know, addition, subtraction when you're buying things. You gotta know how much you're gonna receive or how much you're gonna give back, you know? Taxes and everything.

Here Liliana explained how her teacher, Miss Martinez, influenced her ideas about the usefulness of math. The specific examples she provided focus on money-related utility, specifically, taxes and purchasing ("buying" things, and knowing "how much you're gonna receive...or give back"). When asked what kinds of things she thought math would help her with, Liliana replied, "Just in my career or just anything that I'm—well, buying things, depending what I do I guess and later in the years. And even just teaching other people what it is." Here Liliana again echoed ideas about math as useful for "buying things," also noting usefulness for a potential future career (though she doesn't know what that will be yet) and

for helping to teach others. Initially she mentioned helping her brother in particular, and then later in the interview she noted that she could use math for “helping my cousins or my brother with homework.” This theme of helping others reoccurred several times in the interview, such as when Liliana spoke about using mathematics to help her mom “when we would go, you know, just grocery shopping or anything” and to help her dad in his locksmith shop.

In another part of her interview, Liliana described whether she thought certain math concepts they had worked on during the year were useful. Liliana again emphasized usefulness for careers when she evaluated whether perimeter and area were useful concepts to learn: “depending on what’s your job like.” She also mentioned how that topic could be useful for school tests since she had seen it on tests previously. When discussing the topic of calculating commission and mark-up, she thought it could be useful for “going to the store.” And for three of the topics (adding and multiplying fractions, writing equations, and finding equivalent ratios), she reported that she was “not sure” where you might use them. When shown a range of images of math classrooms and asked whether or not useful math was happening, Liliana often judged usefulness based on whether it was something she had seen in school. For example, when looking at a picture of students hanging graphs they created, Liliana shared, “This one was—I would say...it’s useful. Mainly because I—I’ve seen something similar to this that we’re doing.”

During her interview, Liliana mentioned a range of sources that influenced her thinking about the usefulness of mathematics. When responding to the aforementioned images, Liliana explained why she viewed mathematics she saw in school as generally useful, pointing to her teacher, Miss Martinez. She commented, “Miss Martinez always says that what we learn in math is useful and we’ll need it. So, I guess, that’s it.” At other times, she referenced her parents and media portrayals. For example, when grappling with the potential usefulness—or lack thereof—of graphing, Liliana initially noted, “I didn’t know what we were gonna need it for. Um, and I told my mom and she wasn’t really sure either.” Later, however, she described how graphing was “kind of useful,” suggesting the influence of media portrayals on her perceptions:

I’ve seen, like, movies or TV shows where they’re like, in a business room and they’re showing, like, how much um, how—just like, you know, like, the weekdays and everything. Or how much money they received over the month. So, I guess that’s kind of useful as well.

Liliana also mentioned looking to adults around her to figure out whether mathematics truly is useful. She noted, “We don’t really see a lot of the things we do in—well I haven’t seen a lot of the things we learn in school, what my parents, you know, do when we’re buying things or in general.” She continued, “The people that I talk to never heard of what we’re learning, so I was like, do we really need it?” In this response, Liliana grappled with the narratives she had previously echoed about the usefulness of mathematics, admitting that she didn’t often see the math she learned in school being used by people around her.

Applying a sociohistorical lens to key themes emerging in the case of Liliana

Four primary themes emerged in Liliana's responses. First, she most commonly conceptualized mathematics as useful for careers and money-related activities, such as doing taxes, purchasing, and budgeting. Second, Liliana expressed a desire to help others, especially her family members, and thought about how mathematics could be useful for doing so; those conceptions were focused primarily on helping others to learn math, and helping with career and money-related activities (her mom's grocery shopping and dad's work). Third, Liliana referenced a range of influences on her ideas about usefulness, including media portrayals (via TV or movies, for example) and significant adults in her life (e.g., her mother and teacher). Finally, Liliana expressed both a trust in significant adults in her life, as well as some scepticism, as she worked to make sense of whether math was truly useful in the ways she was hearing, given its visible absence on many occasions.

Applying a sociohistorical perspective to these four primary themes in Liliana's interview reveals several ways in which STEM narratives emphasizing capitalism and global competition influenced Liliana's thinking about the usefulness of mathematics. We are also able to see how she relied on these narratives although they were often in conflict with her experiences and values. To begin, in drawing attention to Liliana's most frequent narratives of mathematics utility—career and money-related activities—Liliana's perceptions serve as a mirror into the dominant narratives of capitalism and economic uses of mathematics (e.g., Harouni, 2015). Relatedly, we see that although Liliana valued helping her family, her ways of conceiving what that might look like were limited to career and money-related activities, as well as simply helping others to learn math. This is not to say that Liliana should not desire to help her mother shop for groceries, help her brother with his math homework, or help her dad in his job; rather, applying this lens highlights how Liliana's conceptions of how mathematics could be used to help others were constrained to conceptions that aligned with dominant sociohistorical narratives (e.g., individual self-interest, economic competition).

Next, when applying this sociohistorical lens, we see how these narratives may have trickled into Liliana's world from larger conversations. Narratives about U.S. global dominance through STEM and preparing a STEM-centric workforce were absorbed and recapitulated by authorities like teachers and popular media, providing Liliana with larger capital-serving narratives (e.g., buying and selling, taxes, or cliché boardroom scenes). Consequently, through this line of communication, Liliana trusted and absorbed these narratives and easily (and often) accessed these narratives when discussing mathematics utility.

Finally, this lens helps us make sense of Liliana's reluctance to wholeheartedly embrace these narratives (including her confusion when working to reconcile Miss Martinez's explanations of usefulness with her observations of the world and conversations with her mother). As discussed above, these dominant narratives about mathematics are inherently exclusionary, even though public messages about the usefulness of STEM often come in the form of blanket statements assumed to apply to all citizens. For example, students are frequently told that STEM learning will be beneficial for their future studies and careers;

however, we know that Black, Latinx, and Indigenous folks are underrepresented in STEM majors and careers (McGee & Bentley, 2017), and so many students lack visible role models who look like them in these areas. Furthermore, society does not truly expect all students to enter STEM careers. Rather, the continuation of racial capitalism actually requires a hierarchy of jobs and the economic exploitation of many racial groups (Morales-Doyle & Gutstein, 2019; Robinson, 2000). Thus, while Liliana heard blanket statements about the usefulness of math, it makes sense that she did not see a wide range of uses of mathematics around her and so questioned the narratives she was hearing.

Reflections on examining usefulness through a sociohistorical lens

Applying a sociohistorical lens to Liliana's talk about the usefulness of mathematics allowed us to see how her conceptions echoed dominant narratives, and helped us to understand her scepticism and questioning. Additionally, applying this lens can make visible narratives that were not voiced. Liliana clearly cared about others and wanted to help others, yet she was only able to see how she could help her cousins and brother to learn math, her mom with grocery shopping, and her dad in his job as a locksmith. She—understandably, given the sociohistorical context—offered no discussion of how math could be used to critically analyse local issues of relevance to her family and community (e.g., Morales-Doyle & Gutstein, 2019; Skovsmose & Valero, 2002). She never mentioned a teacher telling her how mathematics could be used to challenge the status quo and focus on people's needs and interests, rather than the economy's. Furthermore, the emphasis on application of specific techniques and skills at the expense of larger goals focused on cultural competence or deeper understanding of the world, for example, risks actually reducing the relevance of math education (Kollosche, 2017). When contemplating the responses we typically provide to students' questions about the utility of mathematics, Kazemi (2018) questions, "Do we teach mathematics in ways that help students make sense of themselves and their world, to imagine the world as they wish it to be not as it is?" (p. 3).

Applying this sociohistorical lens to students' discussions about the usefulness of mathematics can help to raise questions for both teachers trying to help students see the usefulness of mathematics and researchers investigating the construct of usefulness. As D'Ambrosio (1990) notes, "It is misleading to see mathematics education primarily as something that prepares for a job. Instead it should be looked upon as something that prepares for full citizenship, for the exercise of all the rights and the performance of all the duties associated with citizenship in a critical and conscious way" (p. 21). Applying this lens to our responses to the age-old question of "How is this useful?" suggests that we need to critically examine the words that come out of our mouths and the narratives we've been programmed to repeat. Who, or what, does it serve when our answer is "if you want to become an engineer"? What are potential affordances and constraints of responses focused on buying, selling, and paying bills? And what can be gained from exploring responses that encourage critical analysis of our society and the use of STEM in service of humanity, rather than capital? These questions align with Harouni's (2015) call to explore "the *why* questions

of mathematics” (p. 71). Additionally, researchers conducting utility value interventions should apply this sociohistorical lens to critically examine the examples provided to learners, as well as learners’ own reflections. While this body of research is all about values of the learner, the discussion of values guiding researchers’ and educators’ assumptions related to the usefulness of mathematics has been noticeably absent. We must begin to critically examine whose interests are being served, as well as what is lost, by perpetuating dominant narratives about usefulness, and to take seriously Vossoughi and Vakil’s (2018) question, “Toward what ends?”

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